

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Second dataset delivery

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE DN.9 - SUMMER

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	27/10/2024	First draft	R.Bosio(POLITO)
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0.9			
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SUMMARY

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Dataset

This dataset was developed by integrating the main datasets used by the 4 research modules of the flagship project. The dataset is published and integrated in the repository at <https://github.com/FS-SUMMER/Dataset.git>. The stored data will be used in the development of the digital twin platform of the area chosen as a case study: the Orco Valley.

The dataset is being continuously updated by the research modules and is also being extended outside the Orco Valley territory to include other areas of the NODES territory.

Structure of the dataset

The dataset was organized into macro-categories relating to the main topics of the individual Research Modules:

- Monitoring - RM1
- Co-simulation platform – RM2
- Landslides and Avalanches - RM3
- Digitization of infrastructure, resources availability –RM4

Additional folder related to data from the Piedmont Region's geoportal and some integrated services such as SIRI and Web-Measurements have been added to the repository.

Below is the structure of the repository in which the dataset is stored. Some of the folders listed in the dataset structure are not visible in the repository as they are not yet populated with data.

```
|— Valle Orco/
| |— Monitoraggio/
| | |— Rete Arpa Piemonte/
| | | |— csv/
| | | | |— Monitoraggio-ambientale/
| | | | |— Monitoraggio-idrologico/
| | | | |— Monitoraggio-nivologico/
| | | |— shp/
| | |— SWE/
| | |— tif/
| |— Co-Simulation platform/
| | |— Energy performace model of buildings within a REC/
| | |— Water reservoir modelling/
| |— Frane/
| | |— dati-SIFRAP/
| | | |— shp/
| |— Valanghe/
| | |— shp/
```

- | | | Digitalizzazione delle infrastrutture/
 - | | | | shp/
- | | | Disponibilità della risorsa/
 - | | | | tif/
 - | | | | shp/
 - | | | | zip/
- | | | dati-regione-Piemonte/
 - | | | | shp/
 - | | | | xlsx/
- | | |
- | | |
- | | | Valle Aosta/
 - | | | | Monitoraggio/
 - | | | | | csv_data_Monte_Rosa/
 - | | | | | | Air_temperature/
 - | | | | | | Discharge/
 - | | | | | | Precipitation/
 - | | | | | | Relative_Humidity/
 - | | | | | | Snow_Height/
 - | | | | | | Total_Radiation/
 - | | | | | rasters_Monte_Rosa/
 - | | | | | shp_Monte_Rosa/
 - | | | | | | Bacini/
 - | | | | | | Ghiacciai/
 - | | | | | | Punti_misure/
 - | | | | Valanghe/
 - | | | | | zip/
 - | | |
 - | | | Altre Aree NODES/
 - | | | | Monitoraggio/
 - | | | | | csv_hourly_data/
 - | | | | | | Autosalt_data/
 - | | | | | | Bussoleno_station_monitoring/
 - | | | | | | CRNS_ANAVS/
 - | | | | | | Nivolet_station_monitoring/